

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1880	Johannes Aavik	1910	1910	1952		Estonian philologist and Fennophile who played a significant role in the modernization and development of the Estonian language	1880-1973
1880	Alexander Goldenweiser	1910	1910	1939		Ukrainian-American anthropologist and sociologist	1880-1940
1880	Thomas Griffith Taylor	1911	No	1951		British English geographer, anthropologist and world explorer	1880-1963
1880	Lev Shcherba	1912	1915	1941		Belorussian-Russian linguist and lexicographer specializing in phonetics and phonology	1880-1944
1880	Albert Léon Guérard	1913		1946		French-American prominent scholar of Comparative Literature	1980-1959
1880	Jules Bloch	1914	1914	1951		French linguist	1880-1953
1880	Ivan Grafenauer	1917	1917	1940		Slovenian literary historian and ethnologist of Carinthian Slovene origin	1880-1964
1880	Vladimir Myuller	1918		1941		Russian linguist and lexicographer	1880-1941
1880	Eustace Haydon	1918	1918	1945		Canadian historian of religion and a leader of the humanist movement	1880-1975
1880	Ida C. Ward	1923		1948		British linguist working mainly on African languages who did influential work in the domains of phonology and tonology	1880-1949
1880	Paul Maas	1903	1903	1959		German classical philologist	1880-1964
1880	Hans Tietze	1903	1903	1939		Austrian-American art historian and member of the Vienna School of Art History	1880-1954
1880	Henri Gavel	1903	1903	1953		French Romanist, Hispanist, Occitanist and Bascologist	1880-1959
1880	Friedrich Gundolf	1903	1903	1931		German Jewish literary scholar and poet and one of the best known academics of the Weimar Republic	1880-1931
1880	Dimitrie Gusti	1904	1904	1948		Romanian sociologist, ethnologist, historian, and voluntarist philosopher	1880-1955
1880	Karl Meister	1905	1905	1963		German classical philologist	1880-1963
1880	Hermann Teuchert	1907	1907	1946		German historical linguist	1880-1972
1880	Gunnar Rudberg	1907	1908	1945		Swedish classical philologist	1880-1954
1880	Albert T. Olmstead	1908	1908	1945		American historian and academic, who specialized in Assyriology	1880-1945

1880	Henry Goddard Leach	1908	1908	1950	American Scandinavian studies scholar and civic leader	1880-1970
1881	Walter Kaudern	1910	1910	1942	Swedish zoologist and ethnographer	1881-1942
1881	Henri Focillon	1911	1918	1943	French art historian	1881-1943
1881	Alfred Radcliffe-Brown	1912		1946	British English social anthropologist who developed the theory of structural functionalism and coadaptation	1881-1955
1881	Jakob Sverdrup	1912	1928	1938	Norwegian philologist and lexicographer	1881-1938
1881	Clive Bell	1914		1964	British art critic, associated with formalism and the Bloomsbury Group, developer the art theory known as significant form	1881-1964
1881	Arthur Stanley Tritton	1918	1918	1946	British Arabist	1881-1973
1881	Carl Whiting Bishop	1921	No	1942	American archeologist who specialized in East Asian civilizations	1881-1942
1881	Nancy Lee Swann	1929	1931	1948 w	American Sinologist and curator of the Gest Memorial Chinese Library	1881-1966
1881	Arthur Upham Pope	1904	No	1953	American expert on Iranian art and the editor of the Survey of Persian Art	1881-1969
1881	Wolfgang Aly	1904	1904	1949	German classical philologist	1881-1962
1881	Friedrich Zucker	1904	1904	1961	German classical philologist and papyrologist	1881-1973
1881	Curt Sachs	1904	1904	1959	German-American domiciled musicologist	1881-1959
1881	Ernst Fraenkel	1905	1905	1936	German linguist (Indo-European linguistics and Baltic studies)	1881-1957
1881	Wilhelm Müller-Wismar	1905	1905	1916	German ethnographer	1881-1916
1881	Daniel Jones	1906	No	1949	British phonetician	1881-1967
1881	Arno Poebel	1906	1906	1946	German Assyriologist	1881-1958
1881	Henri Focillon	1906	1906	1943	French art historian	1881-1943
1881	Fernando Ortiz Fernández	1906	No	1969	Cuban essayist, anthropologist, ethnomusicologist and scholar of Afro-Cuban culture	1881-1969
1881	Henri Grégoire	1906		1951	Belgian eminent scholar of the Byzantine Empire, virtually the founder of Byzantine studies	1881-1964
1881	Édouard Paul Dhorme	1907		1951	French Assyriologist, Semitologist and translator of the Bible	1881-1966
1881	Robert Sutherland Rattray	1907	No	1930	British barrister and held a diploma in Anthropology from Oxford	1881-1938
1881	Richard Hartmann	1907	1907	1956	German Orientalist	1881-1965

1881	Arthur C. Parker	1907		1946	American archaeologist, historian, folklorist, museologist and noted authority on American Indian culture	1881-1955
1881	Frank Speck	1908	1908	1949	American Anthropologist and ethnographer	1881-1950
1881	Hans Jantzen	1908	1908	1951	German art historian who specialized in Medieval art	1881-1967
1881	Ludwig Pfandl	1908	1908	1942	German biographer, Hispanist and Romance studies scholar	1881-1942
1881	Sigurd Agrell	1909	1909	1937	Swedish poet, translator, runologist and professor of Slavic languages	1881-1937
1881	Kurt Zoege von Manteuffel	1909	1909	1941	Estonian Baltic German art historian	1881-1941
1881	Eugen Lovinescu	1909	1909	1943	Romanian modernist literary historian, literary critic, academic, and novelist	1881-1943
1882	Lis Jacobsen	1910	1910	1931 w	Danish philologist, archaeologist and writer	1882-1961
1882	Edmond Faral	1910	1910	1955	Algerian-French medievalist	1882-1958
1882	Vincenc Lesný	1912		1953	Czech professor and research scholar of Indology and Iranian Studies	1882-1953
1882	Eva Sachs	1914	1914	1929 w	German classical philologist	1882-1936
1882	Hilary Jenkinson	1915		1954	British archivist and archival theorist, regarded as the figure most responsible for bringing continental European concepts of archival theory to the English-speaking world	1882-1961
1882	Shinkichi Hashimoto	1916		1945	Japanese linguist	1882-1945
1882	Louis Gernet	1917	1917	1952	French philologist and sociologist	1882-1962
1882	Mykolas Biržiška	1918		1949	Lithuanian editor, historian, professor of literature, diplomat, and politician, was one of the twenty signatories of the Act of Independence of Lithuania	1882-1962
1882	Lilias Eveline Armstrong	1922	1922	1937 w	British phonetician	1882-1937
1882	Adolphe Bloch	1898		1952	French biological and racialist anthropologist as well as a Turkologist	1882-1969
1882	Kyōsuke Kindaichi	1902		1954	Japanese linguist	1882-1971
1882	Henry George Farmer	1904	1926	1965	British music historian, composer, conductor and musician (the history of Arabic music, medieval European music theory, Persian and Turkish music as well as the history of European military music and Scottish brass music)	1882-1965

1882 Paul Hambruch	1904	1904	1933	German ethnologist and folklorist	1882-1933
1882 Paul Friedländer	1905	1905	1968	German philologist specializing in classical literature	1882-1968
1882 Fritz Strich	1905		1953	German-Swiss literature historian	1882-1963
1882 Zoltán Kodály	1906	1906	1942	Hungarian composer, ethnomusicologist, pedagogue, linguist, and philosopher	1882-1967
1882 Jakob Jud	1906	1906	1950	Swiss Romance linguist (Romanist)	1882-1952
1882 Vilém Mathesius	1906	1907	1939	Czech linguist, literary historian	1882-1945
1882 Gisela Richter	1906 No		1948 w	British-American classical archaeologist and art historian	1882-1972
1882 Hermann Mutschmann	1906	1906	1918	German classical philologist	1882-1918
1882 Harold H. Bender	1907	1907	1950	American linguist, chair of the Department of Oriental Languages and Literature	1882-1951
1882 Jan Czekanowski	1907	1907	1946	Polish anthropologist, statistician, ethnographer, traveller, and linguist	1882-1965
1882 Carlo Battisti	1908		1954	Italian glottologist, linguist, librarian and academic	1882-1977
1882 Stoyan Romanski	1908	1908	1958	Bulgarian Slavic scientist, ethnographer and secretary of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	1882-1959
1882 Henri Lavachery	1908	1908	1960	Belgian archaeologist and ethnologist	1885-1972
1882 Ernst Sarfert	1908	1908	1918	German ethnologist	1882-1937
1882 John Alexander Stewart	1909	1903	1942	British (Scottish) classical scholar, colonial public servant, and professor of Burmese	1882-1948
1883 Curt Nimuendajú	1910 No		1945	German-Brazilian ethnologist, anthropologist, and writer	1883-1945
1883 Manuel Gamio	1910	1910	1960	Mexican anthropologist, archaeologist, sociologist, and a leader of the indigenismo movement. Although he rejected full sovereignty for indigenous communities in Mexico	1883-1960
1883 André Guimbretière	1911	1919	1960	French linguist and philologist, originator of the linguistic theory known as "psychomechanics"	1883-1960
1883 H. Otley Beyer	1911		1954	American archeologist, the Father of Philippine Anthropology	1883-1966
1883 Paul Radin	1911	1911	1949	American cultural anthropologist and folklorist of the early twentieth century specializing in Native American languages and cultures	1883-1959

1883	Gustave Guillaume	1911	1960	French linguist and philologist, originator of the linguistic theory known as "psychomechanics"	1883-1960	
1883	Marco La Piana	1912	1948	Italian scholar of Arbëresh origin (studies on Albanian language and Arbëresh dialects)	1883-1958	
1883	T. F. O'Rahilly	1913	1947	Irish scholar of the Celtic languages, particularly in the fields of historical linguistics and Irish dialects	1883-1953	
1883	Charles Bruneau	1913	1950	French grammarian, linguist and philologist	1883-1969	
1883	J. J. Smith	1913	1945	South African leading figure in the Afrikaans language movement and the compiler of the first standard Afrikaans dictionary	1883-1949	
1883	Ernest William Hawkes	1913	1957	American anthropologist best known for his work studying the indigenous peoples of Alaska and northern Canada	1883-1957	
1883	Martin Franz Dibelius	1913	1947	German academic theologian and New Testament professor	1883-1947	
1883	Arthur Maurice Hocart	1914	No	1939	British anthropologist best known for his eccentric and often far-seeing works on Polynesia, Melanesia and Sri Lanka	1883-1939
1883	Marius Barbeau	1915	1949	Canadian ethnographer and folklorist (founder of Canadian anthropology)	1883-1969	
1883	C. J. Bulliet	1918	1943	American art critic and author	1883-1952	
1883	Ruth Underhill	1919	1937	1953 w	American anthropologist	1883-1984
1883	Miriam Tildesley	1920	No	1955 w	British English anthropologist	1883-1979
1883	Louis Massignon	1922	No	1954	French Catholic scholar of Islam and a pioneer of Catholic-Muslim mutual understanding	1883-1962
1883	Harold S. Gladwin	1928	1968	American archaeologist, anthropologist, and stockbroker	1883-1983	
1883	Otto Erich Deutsch	1946	1967	Austrian musicologist	1883-1967	
1883	Erica Tietze-Conrat	1905	1905	1949 w	Austrian-American art historian, one of the first women to study art history, a strong supporter of contemporary art in Vienna and an art historian specializing in Renaissance art	1883-1958
1883	Henri Maspero	1906	1944	French sinologist and professor who contributed to a variety of topics relating to East Asia	1883-1945	
1883	Christian Jensen	1906	1906	1940	German classical philologist and papyrologist	1883-1940

1883	Johannes Pedersen	1907	1908	1955	Danish Old Testament scholar and Semitic philologist	1883-1977
1883	Robert Lowie	1908	1908	1950	Austrian-American anthropologist, expert on North American Indians	1883-1957
1883	Karl Barwick	1908	1908	1954	German classical philologist	1883-1965
1883	Gyula Mészáros	1909	1909	1944	Hungarian ethnographer, Orientalist and Turkologist	1883-1957
1884	Herbert Eustis Winlock	1910	No	1939	American Egyptologist employed with the Metropolitan Museum of Art	1884-1950
1884	Rudolf Tschudi	1910	1910	1949	Swiss philologist, historian, and Orientalist	1884-1960
1884	Rudolf Karl Bultmann	1910	1910	1951	German Lutheran theologian and professor of the New Testament	1884-1976
1884	Mary Hamilton Swindler	1912	1912	1949 w	American archaeologist, classical art scholar, author, and professor of classical archaeology	1884-1967
1884	Eugenie Goldstern	1912	1920	1942 w	Ukrainian-Austrian anthropologist who conducted research on Alpine folk culture in Switzerland	1884-1942
1884	Clovis Brunel	1912		1954	French philologist and writer	1884-1971
1884	Eugeniusz Frankowski	1913	1921	1960	Polish archaeologist, ethnographer and ethnologist	1884-1962
1884	Maria Czaplicka	1914		1921 w	Polish cultural anthropologist who is best known for her ethnography of Siberian shamanism	1884-1921
1884	Gudmund Hatt	1914	1914	1947	Danish archaeologist and cultural geographer	1884-1960
1884	Louis Alibert	1914		1944	French linguist and occitanist	1884-1959
1884	David Crockett Graham	1919	1928	1950	American polymath American Baptist minister and missionary, educator, author, archeologist, anthropologist, naturalist and field collector in Szechuan Province	1884-1961
1884	C. H. Dodd	1920		1949	British Welsh New Testament scholar and influential Protestant theologian	1884-1973
1884	Ovid R. Sellers	1923	1924	1954	American Professor of the Old Testament and Dean of McCormick Theological Seminary in Chicago	1884-1975
1884	Davidson Black	1925	No	1934	Canadian paleoanthropologist	1884-1934
1884	Lev V. Oshanin	1931		1962	Russian professor, medical doctor, anthropologist, and founder of the department of anthropology at Tashkent University	1884-1962
1884	Otmar Schissel von Fleschenberg	1906	1907	1937	Austrian philologist	1884-1943

1884	Edgar Roquette-Pinto	1906	No	1936	Brazilian writer, ethnologist, anthropologist and physician	1884-1954
1884	Alexander Mervart	1907	1907	1932	German-Russian indologist, ethnographer, linguist and the first Russian dravidologist	1884-1932
1884	Gyula Germanus	1907	1907	1964	Hungarian professor of oriental studies, writer and Islamologist, member of the Hungarian Parliament and study of the Arabic language, history of language and cultural history	1884-1979
1884	John Peabody Harrington	1908	No	1954	American linguist and ethnologist	1884-1961
1884	Jarl Charpentier	1908	1908	1935	Swedish orientalist and linguist	1884-1935
1884	Otakar Pertold	1908	1908	1948	Czech Indologist, religious studies historian and ethnologist, generally considered the pioneer of Asian religious studies in Czechoslovakia	1884-1965
1884	Paul Lehmann	1908	1908	1950	German paleographer and philologist	1884-1964
1884	Bronisław Malinowski	1908	1908	1942	Pokish anthropologist whose writings on ethnography, social theory, and field research were a lasting influence on the discipline of anthropology	1884-1942
1884	Tomás Navarro Tomás	1908	1908	1952	Spanish philologist, librarian and linguist	1884-1979
1884	Edward Sapir	1909	1909	1939	Lithuanian-American anthropologist-linguist	1884-1939
1884	Oskar Rescher	1909	1909	1949	German-Turkish scholar in Arabic, Persian, and Turkish literature who specialized in pre-Islamic Arabic poetry and Ottoman studies	1884-1972
1884	Salvador Debenedetti	1909	1909	1930	Argentinean archaeologist, anthropologist and educator	1884-1930
1884	George Giuglea	1909	1920	1947	Romanian linguist and philologist	1884-1967